

MODIFIED FICK'S LAW AND TSAI METHOD APPLIED TO THE ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVE BONDED REPAIRED COMPOSITE

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Keywords: Adhesive bonding repair, Composite patch, Coupling, Hygrothermal environment, Moisture absorption

ABSTRACT

The coupled hygro-thermo-stress analysis method on adhesively bonded composite repair under coupled hygrothermal and mechanical loads environment was investigated. A coupled moisture diffusion-strain equation was presented by modifying the Fick's law. A so called "strain diffusion coefficient" and a strain coupling item were introduced into the Fick's equation, which made the coupled moisture diffusion-strain equation. This coupled governing equation can describe the diffusion of composite moisture absorption and model the effect of interactions between complex strain and moisture histories on the diffusion process within composite material more accurately. A modified Tsai method was suggested also. In modified Tsai method, glass transition temperature in dry specimen at room temperature was used as the base value. After modifying, Tsai method highlights the effect of moisture absorption on material property degradation. The modified result is well agreed with experimental result. By using of a transient coupled moisture-temperature-stress FE analysis method, a stepped lap adhesive bonded composite repair under temperature and humidity environment was analyzed. The ultimate loads were obtained under tension load. The results from the numerical simulation were verified by the test. Proposed analytical method for adhesively bonded composite repair in this paper had significance to evaluation of the effectiveness of the composite bonding repair.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite material had the advantages of high ratio of strength and rigidity to weight. But composite materials was easy to damage when under impact. And the composite structural components of commercial aircraft would inevitably encounter damages during the service life. It is important to develop repair techniques in order to restore their original properties to guarantee safety. Adhesive bonding is one of the main approaches for repairing advanced fiber composite components. However, the performance of composite and adhesive patch exposed to combined temperature, humidity and external load environment would degrade greatly [1-3]. There is an urgent need to study the coupled hygro-thermo-stress effects on adhesively bonded composite repair in coupled hygro-thermal and mechanical loads environment.

The experiment research were mainly used to analyse the effect of temperature and humidity environment on bonded repaired composite [4-7]. It was much cost and time consuming. The analytical theory and numerical method were required to simulate the test [8]. The extensive research in the adhesive bonded joint of composite provided a reference for the adhesive bonding repair. Ahmed Al-Shawaf [9] analyzed the thermal stress by using of a temperature and displacement coupling element. An elastic-plastic model was built for adhesive. Crocombe [10-11] utilized the Cohesive Zone Model (CZM) to study the failure mechanism of the interface of composite bonded joints and the durability of bonded composite structures under various moist environment. Hua [12-14] indicated from his research that the CZM could analysis effectively the strength of bonded joint of composite and metal at moist circumstance. Actually the material properties would degrade along with the change of temperature and humidity. And the induced stress would also react on the moisture absorption. The coupling analysis of hygro-thermal-stress of the adhesive bonded repair for composite must be investigated further.

Since moisture could not penetrate fibres, the behaviour of diffusing moisture in composites was usually affected by the resin properties. Fickian diffusion model with a constant, a concentration dependent or a stress dependent diffusion coefficient had been used to describe the moisture transport in composites. Some work showed two-staged sorption behaviour, a non-Fickian transport process, for the fiber reinforced composite. It was well-known that Fick's law was frequently inadequate to describe moisture diffusion in polymers and polymer composites [15-19]. It often exhibit by experiment deviations from the classical Fickian treatment.

The objective of this paper was to investigate the coupling analysis method of hygro-thermal-stress for the adhesive bonded repair for composites. The Fick's law was modified by introduce a strain coupling item to describe the diffusion of composite moisture absorption. A modified Tsai method was also studied to predict the material property degradation. A transient coupled moisture-temperature-stress analysis method was proposed. And the repaired glass fiber composite laminate specimen was analyzed by the suggested method and verified by the experiment.

2 STRAIN-ASSISTED NON-FICKIAN DIFFUSION EQUATION

2.1 Moisture diffusion in composite material

The moisture absorption of composite plate could be simplified as one dimension diffusion as shown in figure 1, since the thickness of the plate was far less than the plane size.

Figure 1: One dimension diffusion of composite material

The Fick equation of one dimension moisture diffusion through the thickness direction is as follow^[20]:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = D_z \cdot \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial z^2}, \quad z \in \left[-\frac{h}{2}, \frac{h}{2}\right] \quad (1)$$

Where, D_z was the moisture diffusion constant along the thickness (z direction) of the material, c was the moisture concentration, t was the time, z was the coordinate through the thickness direction as shown in figure 1, h was the thickness of the laminate.

If c_∞ was assumed the moisture concentration of the environment, the boundary and initial conditions were:

$$\begin{cases} c = c_0, & t = 0 \\ c = c_\infty, & z = \pm \frac{h}{2} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The concentration in the laminate, $c(z_k, t)$, which was function of coordinate z and time t , could be given as:

$$c(z_k, t) = c_\infty - \frac{4c_\infty}{\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n \frac{\cos\left[\frac{(2n+1)\pi \cdot z_k}{h}\right]}{2n+1} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-D_z(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 t}{h^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

2.2 Hygro-thermo-stress in laminate

Combined thermal and moisture induced stresses would be induced in composite laminate under hygrothermal and environment. Since the thermal conductivity of the composite was much larger than the moisture diffusivity, the time required to reach thermal steady-state was far less than to moisture equilibrium. And the combined thermal and moisture induced stress could be considered as linear superposition of transient moisture stress and thermal steady-state stress.

The hygro-thermo-strain in the laminate could be calculated as:

$$\varepsilon_i^{n(k)} = \varepsilon_i^{n(0)} + z_k \cdot \kappa_i^n \quad (4)$$

The residual hygro-thermo-strain was defined as the difference of the hygro-thermo-strain and free deformation, as shown in equation (5)

$$\varepsilon_i^{re(k)} = \varepsilon_i^{n(k)} - e_i^{(k)} \quad (5)$$

Then the residual hygro-thermo-stress of the laminate could be deduced from corresponding strain as:

$$\sigma_i^{re(k)} = Q_{ij} \varepsilon_j^{re(k)} \quad (6)$$

2.3 Strain-assisted moisture diffusion equation

It was now well-known that Fick's law is frequently inadequate for describing moisture diffusion in polymers and polymer composites. Non-Fickian or anomalous diffusion was likely to occur when a polymer was subjected to external stresses and strains, as well as elevated temperatures and humidity.

It was found in the calculation of strain of the laminate that the transverse hygro-thermo-strain ε_{22} was greater than others in the process of moisture absorption. According to the transverse strain and time curve during the moisture absorption of composite laminates, this strain increased linearly with square root of time, which was similar with that between moisture content and time, as displayed in figure 2. Both of the strain and moisture content are linear with time square root. A so called "strain diffusion coefficient" and a strain coupling item were introduced into the Fick's equation, which made the coupled moisture diffusion-strain equation

Figure 2: Hygrothermal strain-time curve in laminate

It could be assumed that the hygro-thermal-strain in laminates also would be “diffuse” as hygro-thermal-stress. And the diffusion coefficient of strain could be calculated as follow:

$$DE = \pi \left(\frac{h}{4\varepsilon_{\infty}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1}{\sqrt{t_2} - \sqrt{t_1}} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

The moisture absorption would reacted by strain diffusion. Introducing the strain diffusion coefficient and the coupling term into the Fick equation, the strain assisted moisture diffusion equation was built as equation (8):

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(D_z \frac{\partial c}{\partial z} + DE \frac{\partial \varepsilon_{22}}{\partial z} \right), \quad z \in \left[-\frac{h}{2}, \frac{h}{2} \right] \quad (8)$$

The analytical solution was difficult to obtain as c was coupling with ε_{22} . Numerical solution by finite difference method was employed.

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial^2 c(z,t)}{\partial z^2} &\approx \frac{1}{(\Delta z)^2} [c(z-\Delta z,t) - 2c(z,t) + c(z+\Delta z,t)] + o((\Delta z)^2) \\ \frac{\partial c(z,t)}{\partial t} &\approx \frac{1}{\Delta t} [c(z,t+\Delta t) - c(z,t)] + o(\Delta t) \\ \frac{\partial^2 \varepsilon(z,t)}{\partial z^2} &\approx \frac{1}{(\Delta z)^2} [\varepsilon(z-\Delta z,t) - 2\varepsilon(z,t) + \varepsilon(z+\Delta z,t)] + o((\Delta z)^2)\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

Where Δz indicated the space increment and Δt indicated the time increment. And $u = D \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta z)^2} \leq \frac{1}{2}$ was satisfied to guarantee convergence.

The moisture diffusion equation in the difference form was

$$\begin{aligned}c(z,t+\Delta t) &= c(z,t) + D_z \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta z)^2} [c(z-\Delta z,t) - 2c(z,t) + c(z+\Delta z,t)] \\ &+ DE \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta z)^2} [\varepsilon(z-\Delta z,t) - 2\varepsilon(z,t) + \varepsilon(z+\Delta z,t)]\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

The procedure about the calculation of strain-assisted moisture diffusion coupling with strain was concluded as follow:

- 1) To calculate the moisture content of the laminate by Fick equation according the initial and boundary conditions.
- 2) To calculate the transvers hygro-thermal strain ε_{22} of laminate under temperature and moisture by classical laminate theory.
- 3) To get the strain diffusion coefficient DE by fitting the $\varepsilon_{22}-\sqrt{t}$ curve.
- 4) To recalculate the moisture content and residual hygro-thermal stress by putting the DE and strain coupling term into the moisture diffusion and strain assisted coupling equation.
- 5) To obtain the moisture content-time curve of laminate.

Figure 3 showed the scheme of coupled moisture diffusion-strain calculating.

Figure 3: Scheme of coupled moisture diffusion-strain calculating

The results by the strain-assisted moisture diffusion equation were displayed in figure 4 and were compared with the tests and results from Fick's. As shown in figure 4, the results from the strain-assisted coupling equation agree well with the experiment. And it improved effectively over estimation of moisture content in the material at initial period and underestimate the material moisture absorption ability in the subsequent process.

Figure 4: Moisture content-time curve of laminate

3 TRANSIENT COUPLED MOISTURE-TEMPERATURE-STRESS ANALYSIS

The temperature field and humidity field through two ways to affect the stress field. One is the material properties and the temperature, humidity conditions; the other was the thermal and moisture expansion and swelling would produce temperature induced stress field. The reaction of the stress field onto heat conduction and moisture diffusion was ignored in this study.

3.1 Modified Tsai method

Material properties were related with the temperature and humidity in hygrothermal environment. Usually the degraded properties of composites influenced by temperature and humidity were analysed by using Tsai method^[21]. The degraded properties of unidirectional laminate were estimated according the power function of T^* , which was a dimensionless coefficient correlation with temperature and humidity, defined as:

$$T^* = (T_g - T_{opr}) / (T_g - T_{ref}) \quad (11)$$

Where $T_g = T_g^0 - g \times m(t)$ was the glass transition temperature of the wet material; $m(t)$ was the percentage of moisture absorption at time t ; T_g^0 was the glass transition temperature of the dry material; g was the material constant; T_{opr} was the test temperature; T_{ref} was the reference temperature, generally standard room temperature.

Then the material properties could be degraded as follow:

$$E_m = E_m^0 \cdot (T^*)^a, \quad \frac{E_f}{E_f^0} = \frac{G_f}{G_f^0} = (T^*)^f \quad (12)$$

$$X_T = X_T^0 \cdot \frac{\nu_f}{\nu_f^0} \cdot (T^*)^h, \quad X_C = X_C^0 \cdot \frac{G_f}{G_f^0} \cdot (T^*)^e, \quad \frac{Y_T}{Y_T^0} = \frac{Y_C}{Y_C^0} = \frac{S}{S^0} = (T^*)^c$$

- Where E_m^0 and E_f^0 was the elastic modulus of matrix and fiber, G_f^0 the shear modulus of fiber, ν_f^0 the Poisson ration, G_{xy}^0 the plane modulus of unidirectional laminate, X_T^0 and X_C^0 the strength of tension and compression along 0° direction of unidirectional laminate, Y_T^0 与 Y_C^0 the strength of tension and compression along 90° direction of unidirectional laminate, S^0 the plane shear strength of unidirectional laminate, in standard room temperature and dry circumstance; E_m , E_f , G_f , ν_f , G_{xy} , X_T , X_C , Y_T , Y_C and S were the degraded material properties in hygro-thermal environment accordingly; a , f , h , e and c were empirical parameters^[2].

The properties dominated by matrix would be affected greatly in hygro-thermal circumstance. In modified Tsai method, the denominator $T_g - T_{ref}$ was revised as $T_g^0 - T_{ref}$, i.e. the T_g^0 was used instead T_g :

$$T^* = (T_g - T_{opr}) / (T_g^0 - T_{ref}) \quad (13)$$

The calculated properties was displayed in figure 5. The results by modified Tsai method was more close to the experimental data than the original Tsai method. The improved Tsai method could highlight the influence of moisture content on the material performance degradation

Figure 5: Tsai method and modified Tsai method

3.2 Analysis of hygro-therm-stress

When the temperature field and humidity field exists at the same time, the constitutive relation of unidirectional composite laminates was as follows

$$\sigma = [D] \varepsilon - [D]\{\alpha\}\Delta T - [D]\{\beta\}\Delta c \quad (14)$$

Where $[D]$ was the elastic matrix; σ was the stress vector; ε was the strain vector; $\{\alpha\}$ was the thermal expansion coefficient vector; $\{\beta\}$ was the moisture expansion coefficient vector; ΔT was the temperature difference; Δc was the moisture concentration difference.

If the nodal force vector was $\{f\}$, displacement vector was $\{u\}$, geometry matrix was $[B]$, then the strain vector would be $\varepsilon = u^T [B]^T$. The total potential energy could be written as:

$$\Pi = \frac{1}{2} \{u\}^T \cdot \left(\int_V [B]^T [D] [B] dV \cdot \{u\} - \int_V [B]^T [D] \{\alpha\} \Delta T dV - \int_V [B]^T [D] \{\beta\} \Delta c dV - 2 \{f\} \cdot \{u\} \right) \quad (15)$$

According to the principle of minimum potential energy $\frac{\partial \Pi}{\partial \{u\}} = 0$, Equation (6) was obtained.

$$\{f\} = \int_V [B]^T [D] [B] dV \cdot \{u\} - \int_V [B]^T [D] \{\alpha\} \Delta T dV - \int_V [B]^T [D] \{\beta\} \Delta c dV \quad (16)$$

Where $\int_V [B]^T [D] [B] dV = [K]$, was the element stiffness matrix. It could be rewritten as:

$$\{f\} + \{f^{\Delta T}\} + \{f^{\Delta c}\} = [K] \{u\} \quad (17)$$

Where $\{f^{\Delta T}\} = \int_V [B]^T [D] \{\alpha\} \Delta T dV$ called the thermal load, $\{f^{\Delta c}\} = \int_V [B]^T [D] \{\beta\} \Delta c dV$ called the moisture load.

Superimposing the thermal load and the moisture load onto the load of the nodes, the finite element analysis coupling moisture, thermal and force could be implemented.

In the finite element analysis of coupled moisture-thermal-force, an element for laminate or adhesive would have DOF of mechanical, thermal and moisture concentration. The temperature-stress coupling module in commercial software ABAQUS could be used in this study, since the mathematical equation for moisture-stress and temperature-stress had the similar form.

The procedure of transient coupled moisture-temperature-stress analysis was displayed in figure 6.

Figure 6: Coupled moisture-temperature-stress analysis method

4 ANALYSIS OF ADHESIVE BONDED REPAIRED COMPOSITE

A repaired glass fiber composite laminate specimen was analyzed. Figure 7 gave its geometry and finite element model. The diameter D of damaged area was 12.7mm. A stepped repair was taken. The layup of host structure was $[45/-45]_{4s}$. The layup of repair patch was $[45/-45]_{2s}$. The thickness of composite lamina was 0.25mm. The thickness of adhesive was 0.125mm. The host laminate and patch were all glass fiber composite material.

Figure 7: The geometry and 3-D FEA model of stepped repair specimen

The coupling moisture-thermal-force analysis was applied to the specimen on which a tension force was acted under different hygro-thermal conditions. The results and the relative errors of analysis and experiment were given in table 1.

Condition	Test	Analysis	relative error /%
Dry, 23 °C	10.596	10.832	2.2
Dry, 82 °C	8.741	9.714	11.1
Wet, 23 °C	8.295	9.152	10.3
Wet, 82 °C	4.932	5.342	8.3

Table 1: Ultimate load under different hygrothermal conditions (kN)

The relative errors were acceptable for engineering. The verified method was used to simulate the repaired laminate bearing mechanical, thermal and moisture loadings. The ultimate loads under various hygro-thermal circumstances were obtained and exhibited in figure 8.

Figure 8: The effects of temperature and humidity on ultimate tensile force

The three coordinates in figure 8 were respectively temperature, moisture concentration and ultimate load. In this analysis, the ultimate load in dry and room temperature was greatest. Along with the increase of temperature and moisture, the altitude of the quadrilateral surface decreased. At the diagonal point, the ultimate load reached the lowest, which means the ultimate load capability for the specimen reduced greatly under the combined action of temperature and wet. Such a result surface could give valuable reference for application.

5 CONCLUSION

A coupling analysis method of hygro-thermal-stress for the adhesive bonded repair for composites was investigated. In this method, a coupled moisture diffusion-strain equation was presented by modifying the Fick's law. It could describe the diffusion of composite moisture absorption and model the effect of interactions between complex strain and moisture histories on the diffusion process within composite material more accurately. The degradation of the mechanical properties for composite after exposure to temperature and the moisture was analyzed by modified Tsai method. The improved Tsai method could highlight the influence of moisture content on the material performance degradation. The results were more closed to experiment. The proposed transient coupled moisture-temperature-stress

analysis method was applied to a stepped lap adhesive bonded repaired composite under temperature and humidity environment. The results from the numerical simulation were verified by the according test. This study had significance to evaluation of the effectiveness of the composite bonding repair.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tounsi A and Adda-Bedia E A, Simplified method for prediction of transient hygroscopic stresses in polymer matrix composites with symmetric environmental conditions, *Applied Composite Materials*, **10**, 2003, pp. 1-18.
- [2] Benkeddad A, Tounsi A and Adda-Bedia E A, Effect of temperature and humidity on transient hygrothermal stresses during moisture desorption in laminated composite plates, *Composite Structure*, **82**, 2008, pp. 629-635.
- [3] Arao Y, Koyanagi J, Utsunomiya S, et al, Time-dependent out-of-plane deformation of UD-CFRP in humid environment, *Composite Science and Technology*, **69**, 2009, pp. 1720-1725.
- [4] Charalambides M N, Hardouin R, Kinloch A J et al, Adhesively-bonded repairs to fibre-composite materials I: Experimental, *Composite Part A*, **29(A)**, 1998, pp. 1371-1381.
- [5] Charalambides M N, Kinloch A J and Matthews, Adhesively-bonded repairs to fibre-composite materials II: Finite element modelling, *Composite Part A*, **29(A)**, 1998, pp. 1383-1396.
- [6] Megueni A, Tounsi A, Bachir B B et al, The effect of a bonded hygrothermal aged composite patch on the stress intensity factor for repairing cracked metallic structures, *Composite Structures*, **62**, 2003, pp. 171-176.
- [7] Marouani S, Curtil L and Hamelin P, Ageing of carbon/epoxy and carbon/vinylester composites used in the reinforcement and/or the repair of civil engineering structures, *Composite Part B*, **43(B)**, 2012, pp. 2020-2030.
- [8] He X C, A review of finite element analysis of adhesively bonded joints, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, **31**, 2011, pp. 248-264.
- [9] Al-Shawaf A, Modeling wet lay-up CFRP-steel bond failure at extreme temperatures using stress-based approach, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, **31**, 2011, pp. 416-428.
- [10] Crocombe A D, Durability modeling concepts and tools cohesive environmental degradation of structures, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, **17**, 1997, pp. 229-238.
- [11] Crocombe A D, Hua Y, Loh W K, et al, Predicting the residual strength for environmentally degraded adhesive lap joints, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, **26**, 2006, pp. 325-336.
- [12] Hua Y, Crocombe A D, Wahab M A, et al, Modeling environmental degradation in EA9321-Bonded joints using a progressive damage failure model, *The Journal of Adhesion*, **82**, 2006, pp. 135-160.
- [13] Hua Y, Crocombe A D, Wahab M A, et al, Continuum damage modeling of environmental degradation in joints bonded with E32 epoxy adhesive, *The Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **21(2)**, 2007, pp. 179-195.
- [14] Hua Y, Crocombe A D, Wahab M A, et al, Continuum damage modeling of environmental degradation in joints bonded with E9321 epoxy adhesive, *International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives*, **82**, 2008, pp. 302-313.
- [15] Weitsman Y J, Anomalous fluid sorption in polymeric composites and its relation to fluid-induced damage, *Composites Part A*, **37**, 2006, pp. 617-623.
- [16] Derrien K and Gilormini P, The effect of applied stresses on the equilibrium moisture content in polymers, *Scripta Materialia*, **56**, 2007, pp. 297-299.
- [17] Fan X J, Lee S W R, et al, Experimental investigations and model study of moisture behaviors in polymeric materials, *Microelectronics Reliability*, **49**, 2009, pp. 861-871.
- [18] Boualem N and Sereir Z, Accelerated aging of unidirectional hybrid composites under the long-term elevated temperature and moisture concentration, *Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics*, **55**, 2011, pp. 68-75.
- [19] Zafar A, Bertocco, et al, Investigation of the long term effects of moisture on carbon fiber and epoxy matrix composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, 2012, pp. 656-666.

- [20] Lee M C and Peppas N A, Models of moisture transport and moisture-induced stresses in epoxy composite, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **27**, 1993, pp. 1146-1171.
- [21] Tsai S W, *Composite Design*, 4th ed. Dayton: Think Composites, 1988.